

Complexes of nickel-, copper-, zinc-, cadmium- and mercury(II) with salicylaldehyde-4,4-dimethyl-3-thiosemicarbazone

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Complexes of salicylaldehyde-4,4-dimethyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (H_2 saldmtsc) with bivalent metal ions of composition $[M(\text{saldmtsc}) \cdot nH_2O]$ ($M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}$ or Hg^{II} and $n = 0$ or 1), $[M(\text{saldmtsc})py]$ ($M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ or Zn^{II}) and $[Ni(\text{saldmtsc})B]$ ($B = \alpha-, \beta-$ or γ -picoline) have been prepared and characterised.

Complexes of transition and non-transition metals with thiosemicarbazides and their Schiff bases have been studied extensively¹. The Schiff bases of thiosemicarbazides, in which both of the hydrogen atoms of N^4 atom are substituted with alkyl or aryl groups, have not been investigated in detail^{2,3}. Here we report the preparation and characterisation of the complexes of bivalent Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg with salicylaldehyde-4,4-dimethyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (H_2 saldmtsc).

Results and Discussion

The ligand-metal stoichiometry indicates that the ligand coordinates as a dianionic tridentate molecule forming monoligated neutral complexes with bivalent metal ions. The complexes are quite stable in air. The adduct complexes $[M(\text{saldmtsc})py]$ ($M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$ or Cd^{II}) and $[Ni(\text{saldmtsc})B]$ ($B = \alpha-, \beta-$ or γ -picoline) as well as the aquo complexes $[M(\text{saldmtsc}) \cdot H_2O]$ ($M = Ni^{II}$ or Zn^{II}) do not lose base or water molecule below $80-90^\circ$, indicating the bonding of the base as well as water molecule in these complexes. The adduct complexes are fairly soluble in organic solvents chloroform, dioxan, benzene and DMF, but the aquo complexes $[M(\text{saldmtsc}) \cdot H_2O]$ ($M = Zn^{II}$ or Ni^{II}) and the complexes $[M(\text{saldmtsc})]$ ($M = Cu^{II}$ or Cd^{II}) are almost insoluble in chloroform, methanol, ethanol and benzene, though dissolve appreciably in DMF. The insolubility of the $[M(\text{saldmtsc}) \cdot H_2O]$ and $[M(\text{saldmtsc})]$ in non-polar solvents indicates the polymeric or dimeric character of these complexes. The DMF solutions of the complexes show molar conductance values in the range of $5-9 \Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ supporting their non-ionic character^{2,3}.

The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes as well as the base adduct complexes of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Ni^{II} are diamagnetic, while the aquo complex $[Ni(\text{saldmtsc}) \cdot H_2O]$ and com-

plexes $[Cu(\text{saldmtsc})Py]$ and $[Cu(\text{saldmtsc})]$ are paramagnetic. The diamagnetism of $[Ni(\text{saldmtsc})B]$ suggests their four-coordinated planar structure⁴. The aquo complex $[Ni(\text{saldmtsc}) \cdot H_2O]$ displays room temperature magnetic moment value of 1.08 B.M. indicating some distorted octahedral Ni^{II} species formed by polymerisation of some planar Ni^{II} molecule similar to various tridentate Schiff base complexes of nickel(II)⁵. The base adduct complex $[Cu(\text{saldmtsc})Py]$ displays the magnetic moment value of 2.01 B.M. at 304 K indicating that the complex is magnetically dilute. The base free complex $[Cu(\text{saldmtsc})]$ displays subnormal magnetic moment value (1.2 B.M.) indicating δ -bonding or super-exchange interaction⁶ and the complex is probably dimeric. The analogous Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are also dimeric. The coordination number four of $[M(\text{saldmtsc})]$ ($M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}$ or Hg^{II}) is completed by the ligand bridging probably through deprotonated phenolic oxygen. The solid reflectance spectra of the complexes show medium or weak bands in the visible region. The electronic bands of both the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are similar to those of planar complexes⁷. In case of dark brown $[CuL]$, the reflectance bands are not well resolved in the visible region due to strong charge transfer absorption.

The ir ligand bands at 3220 (OH) and 3295 cm^{-1} (NH) disappear in almost all the complexes, suggesting deprotonation of both phenolic OH and thioamide NH protons on complexation. The ligand band at 1215 cm^{-1} (C-O) is raised to a higher frequency at 1360-1385 cm^{-1} in the mononuclear complexes $[M(\text{saldmtsc})B]$ which indicates that the bond order of phenolic C-O is raised on coordination as usually observed in salicylaldehyde Schiff base complexes⁸. A large shift in C-O stretch (1590-1530 cm^{-1}) in the dimeric complexes suggests that phenolic oxygen is acting as bridging atom. The shifting of $\nu_{C=N}$ of

aldimine group (1620 cm^{-1}) to lower frequency indicates the involvement of aldimine (C=N) nitrogen atom in coordination. The thioamide bands I, II and III of the free ligand located at 1540 , 1337 and 1153 cm^{-1} are raised to higher frequencies suggesting the coordination of the thioamide group with metal atoms⁹. The thioamide band IV (898 cm^{-1}) suggests the existence of ligand in thione tautomer and this band is shifted to a lower frequency by 170 – 190 cm^{-1} indicating that the thioamide sulphur is bonded to metal atom by deprotonation of the thiol tautomer.

The aquo complexes display a broad and medium band at 3430 – 3450 cm^{-1} for $\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ and a broad band at $680 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to $\rho_{\omega}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ of the coordinated water molecule¹¹. The presence of pyridine ring breathing mode vibration at $1008 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in pyridine and picoline adduct complexes indicates coordinated nature of the pyridine and picoline molecules in the complexes¹². The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band of the coordinated pyridine molecule could not be located separately as it merges with the ligand $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ vibration. In far-ir spectrum, the new bands located at 530 – 460 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$. The weak bands at 355 – 380 and 390 – 310 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to (M–N) and (M–S) stretches in the complexes. The energy of the bands observed for (M–O), (M–N) and (M–S) stretches occur in the range of reported values¹³. Hence it is suggested that in all the complexes, ($\text{H}_2\text{ saldmisc}$) is coordinated as a dianionic tridentate molecule and bonded to the metal atom through O, N and S atoms. In the dimeric complexes the phenolic oxygen is the bridging atom.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by refluxing molar proportion of 4,4-dimethyl-1,3-thiosemicarbazide² with salicylaldehyde in ethanol on a steam-bath for 0.5 h. The product was crystallised from hot ethanol, m.p. 196° (Found : N, 18.67. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{SO}$ requires : N, 18.83%).

$[\text{M}(\text{saldmisc})_n\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($n = 1$ for $\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{II}$ or Zn^{II} and 0 for $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{II}$, Cd^{II} or Hg^{II}): The hydrated metal chloride or acetate (0.01 mol) dissolved in 90% aqueous methanol (40 ml) was refluxed with methanol solution of the ligand (0.01 mol containing 2–3 g sodium acetate) on a steam-bath for ~30 min when the complex separated gradually. It was washed with aqueous methanol and dried over CaCl_2 .

$[\text{M}(\text{saldmisc})\text{Py}]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{II}$, Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}) and $[\text{Ni}(\text{saldmisc})\text{B}]$ ($\text{B} = \alpha$ -, β -, or γ -picoline): A mixture of methanolic solution (40–50 ml) of the metal chloride or acetate (0.01 mol) and the appropriate pyridine (4–5 ml) was refluxed with methanol solution (30–40 ml) of the ligand (0.01 mol) for 15 min on a steam-bath. The mixture was then cooled and the resulting complex was washed with methanol containing a few drops of the appropriate base and dried in a desiccator over KOH.

Magnetic moment and spectral data were recorded as reported earlier³.

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